

Synthesis of Pericarbonyl Lignans and Their Analogues

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Perkin condensation of β -benzoylpropionic acid system (VI) and aryl aldehyde gave butenolide (VII) which led to α -arylidene- β -benzoylpropionic acid (IX). The latter, on formylation followed by cyclization afforded chloromethylnaphthoic acid (XV). Chloromethyl derivatives (XV) were subsequently converted into pericarbonyl lactones (XVI). This approach exemplifies a simple synthetic route to 1-aryl-2,3-naphthalide pericarbonyl lignans.

NATURAL products based on 2,3-dimethylphenyl-naphthalene constitute a distinct class of lignans. More than 10 members, dehydropodophyllotoxin^{1a}, diphyllin^{1b-1d}, justicidin D^{1h} (neojusticidin^{1e}), justicidin E^{1j,k}, taiwanin A¹ⁱ, taiwanin C^{1m} and helioxanthin¹ⁿ, are now well characterized. All are lactones of either 1-phenyl-2-hydroxymethylnaphthalene-3-carboxylic acid (pericarbonyl lactone) (I) or 1-phenyl-3-hydroxymethylnaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid (perimethylene lactone) (II). Some of the aryl-naphthalide lignans were found to be physiologically active. Prominent among them are diphyllin² and justicidins A and B which are fish poisons, the latter being comparable to rotenone in toxicity in *Orizius latipus*³. Diphyllin completely inhibited DNA synthesis in Ehrlich carcinoma cells within a minute and partially inhibited RNA and protein formation⁴. The synthesis of some aryl-naphthalide lignans with pericarbonyl grouping is reported here.

An earlier attempt⁵ to prepare the system of the type (I) by condensation of dimethylbenzoylsuccinate (III) and aryl aldehyde proceeded with the loss of carbomethoxy group leading to α -arylidene- β -benzoylpropionate (IV) which was later converted into pericarbonyl system (I).

To prepare pericarbonyl lactone (I) it was endeavoured to use β -aroylpropionic acid system (VI) which has two reactive methylene groups and a carboxy function capable of being handled to lead to the basic skeleton of lignan (VIII). A carbomethoxy group would yield part of furan ring adjacent to ring B and oxo group could be reduced.

Perkin condensation of β -benzoylpropionic acid (VI) with aryl aldehyde yielded butenolide of the type (VII) which finally led to α -arylidene- β -benzoylpropionic acid (IX). The butenolides (VII) were highly insoluble in most solvents, non-acidic to bicarbonate, but slowly dissolved in sodium hydroxide. Equivalent weight determination was not satisfactory (the products were highly insoluble and slight decomposition occurred). Using substituted benzoylpropionic acids and different aryl aldehydes, a number of butenolides were synthesized. These compounds showed an extended conjugation

at 400 nm in their ultraviolet spectra⁶. IR spectra of these compounds showed characteristic absorption at 1775 to 1760 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl⁷) and nmr showed all protons in the expected region 6.58 to 7.58 δ (Table 1).

When the butenolide corresponding to benzaldehyde (VII; $R_1=R_2=R'=H$) was treated with 30% sodium hydroxide with subsequent acidification, the products isolated were benzaldehyde and benzoic acid, respectively. A retro reaction occurred⁸. The butenolides (VII) were hence cleaved by refluxing in methanolic sodium carbonate (Borsche⁹), on acidification, afforded dark coloured mass which crystallized from aqueous alcohol to give α -arylidene- β -benzoylpropionic acids (IX). The IR spectra of IX showed a single absorption at 1681 cm^{-1} (aryl conjugated carbonyl and α,β -unsaturated acid^{10,11}) (Table 2).

The stereochemistry of formation of α -arylidene- β -benzoylpropionic acids by Perkin condensation of β -benzoylpropionic acids with aryl aldehyde has E or *cis* Ar/CH₂COPh structure (X)⁸. The stereochemistry of the product would be controlled by the transition state in the Perkin reaction having the conformation with the bulky Ar and COOR groups *trans* which undergoes *trans* elimination of acetic acid to give the product (XI)^{10,11}, with *cis* (E) Ar/CH₂COPh stereochemistry. Zimmerman orbital overlap theory¹² also leads to the same stereochemistry. For the overlap control, the carbonyl group must lie in the plane of the incipient double bond between the carbon 2 and 3. Out of the two transition states, (XII) and (XIII), which are possible in Perkin reaction (XII) would lead to *cis* (E) Ar/CH₂COPh. In the transition state (XII), the planarity which is necessary for orbital overlap is readily achieved as carbonyl group is unhindered. But in the case of (XIII), there is steric interaction of *cis* aryl/carbonyl groups which pushes the carbonyl group out of plane of the incipient double bond (XIIIa). So, the planarity is less readily achieved and consequently the overlap control is less. Thus the transition state (XII) is more favourable.

α -Arylidene- β -benzoylpropionic acid system (IX) thus obtained contained the required skeleton to prepare pericarboxyl lactone system. Elements of furan ring adjacent to ring B were introduced by formylation. Acid (IX) was treated with aqueous formaldehyde and potassium hydroxide to give the product which was identified as α -arylidene- β -methylene- β -benzoylpropionic acid (XIV). [Kulkarni^{13,14} observed that alkali concentration in the reaction play an important role in the formation of either mono or dicondensation product]. IR spectra of XIV showed a broad peak at 1660 cm^{-1} for carboxyl and keto groups. In the nmr spectrum, two methylene protons appeared as a singlet at

6.06δ , and a singlet at 7.85δ was assigned for olefinic proton (Table 3).

To cyclize the α -arylidene- β -methylene- β -benzoylpropionic acid system (XIV) to 1-phenyl-naphthalene system, it was treated with a mixture of acetic acid and conc. hydrochloric acid to give a product which was characterized as 1-phenyl-2-chloromethyl-naphthalene-3-carboxylic acid (XV). IR spectra of chloromethyl derivatives (XV) showed a peak at 1670 cm^{-1} for a carboxyl group. NMR spectra showed a singlet at 5.08δ for chloromethyl protons. The proton at C_8 appeared as a singlet at 6.68δ . The proton at C_4 showed a singlet at 8.74δ . A

Scheme 2

singlet due to C_α proton at 7.35 δ is merged in aromatic pattern in the region 7.3-7.7 δ (Table 4).

Chloromethyl derivatives (XV) were hydrolysed by heating with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide. Then they were treated with excess of hydrochloric acid and heated at 100° for 0.5 hr. After cooling, the solid was isolated and identified as 1-phenyl-2-hydroxymethylnaphthalene-3-carboxylic acid lactone (XVI). In ir spectra of XVI, absorption at 1760 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of 5-membered lactone ring¹⁶. The nmr spectra are also consistent with the structures assigned to them. 4-H proton resonates close to 8.38 δ (compared to 7.7 δ in retro lactone¹⁴) whilst methylene group of lactone¹⁷ is shielded by ring current. This is seen by the chemical shift near 5.10 δ in contrast to 5.40 δ in the retro lactone (Table 5).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were run on Perkin-Elmer 237 grating machine in nujol and uv on Beckmann DB-4 spectrophotometer in ethanol unless otherwise stated. NMR spectra were measured at 60 MHz using deuteriochloroform (CDCl_3) as the solvent, the

chemical shifts are given in ppm using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard.

1. Perkin condensation of β -benzoylpropionic acid and veratraldehyde; α -(3,4-Dimethoxybenzylidene)- γ -phenyl- $\Delta\beta,\gamma$ -butenolide (VIIa, $R_1=R_2=\text{OCH}_3$, $R'=\text{H}$):

Veratraldehyde (4.2 g; 0.025 m) and β -benzoylpropionic acid (4.9 g; 0.025m) were refluxed for 3 hr in presence of acetic anhydride (7.5 ml) and a drop of pyridine. The hot reaction mixture was added to cold water (100 ml) and was warmed for a minute, cooled to 0°, filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from benzene to give α -(3,4-dimethoxybenzylidene)- γ -phenyl- $\Delta\beta,\gamma$ -butenolide (VIIa), m.p. 125°. UV: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 249 nm, $\log \epsilon$ 4.21, 3.91 nm, $\log \epsilon$ 4.21 an shoulder 406 nm, $\log \epsilon$ 4.24. (Found: C, 73.56; H, 5.96. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$; C, 74.02; H, 5.23%. Table 1 presents the data for other butenolides (VIIa-VIIr).

2. α -(3,4-Dimethoxybenzylidene)- β -benzoylpropionic acid (IXa, $R_1=R_2=\text{OCH}_3$, $R'=\text{H}$):

α -(3,4-Dimethoxybenzylidene)- γ -phenyl- $\Delta\beta,\gamma$ -butenolide (VIIa) (5 g) was refluxed with alcoholic sodium carbonate solution for 5 hr. The resulting mixture was cooled, filtered and acidified to congo

TABLE 1— α -ARYLIDENE- γ -PHENYL- $\Delta\beta,\gamma$ -BUTENOLIDES (VII)
Condensation of β -Aroylpropionic Acid with Aldehydes

Sl. No.	Aldehyde g	β -Aroyl-propionic acid g	Lactone g	Yield %	m.p. °C	UV $E_{1\%}^{1\text{cm}}$ nm (log ϵ)	IR cm^{-1}	NMR δ	Analysis %			
									Found		Calcd	
									C	H	C	H
1.	Veratraldehyde 8.3	β -Benzoyl-propionic acid 8.9	(VIIa) 14.11	73.3	125	249 (4.21) 392 (4.32) 406 (4.24)	— —	—	73.56	5.96	74.02	5.23
2.	Veratraldehyde 8.3	4-Methoxy-benzoyl-propionic acid 10.4	(VIIb) 14.6	82.8	172	—	—	—	70.59	5.17	71.00	5.36
3.	Veratraldehyde 8.3	4-Methyl-benzoyl-propionic acid 9.6	(VIIc) 12.1	75.1	170	—	—	—	74.14	5.28	74.53	5.63
4.	Vanillin 7.1	β -Benzoyl-propionic acid 8.9	(VII d) 13.7	85.6	147	252 (4.18) 393 (4.26)	—	—	—	—	—	—
5.	Vanillin 7.1	4-Methoxy-benzoyl-propionic acid 10.4	(VII e) 11.7	72.2	188	—	—	—	70.12	4.58	70.37	4.97
6.	Vanillin 7.1	4-Methyl-benzoyl-propionic acid 9.6	(VII f) 13.1	85.0	156	—	—	—	74.22	4.95	74.01	5.23
7.	Vanillin 7.1	4-Isopropyl-benzoyl-propionic acid 11.0	(VII g) 11.5	77.0	122	—	—	—	74.79	6.03	74.97	5.99
8.	Vanillin 7.1	4-Chloro-benzoyl-propionic acid 10.6	(VII h) 11.5	70.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
9.	Vanillin 7.1	4-Bromo-benzoyl-propionic acid 8.9	(VII i) 13.2	63.2	128	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
10.	4-Methoxy-benzaldehyde 6.8	β -Benzoyl-propionic acid 8.9	(VII j) 13.2	84.1	169	245 (4.28) 290 (4.20) 402 (4.23)	1772 1762	3.87 (s, 3H, OCH ₃) 7.11-7.06 (m, 9H aromatic), 6.92 (s, 2H, olefinic)	77.66	5.07	77.69	5.07
11.	3-Methoxy-benzaldehyde 6.8	β -Benzoyl-propionic acid 10.4	(VII k) 14.0	81.3	120	—	—	—	77.18	5.27	77.69	5.07
12.	3-Methoxy-benzaldehyde 6.8	4-Methoxy-benzoyl-propionic acid 10.4	(VII l) 11.0	71.4	135	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
13.	Piperonal 7.5	β -Benzoyl-propionic acid 8.9	(VII m) 14.0	85.4	166	254 (4.12) 404 (4.46)	1772 1862	6.03 (s, 2H, -OCH ₂ O-) 7.85-6.91 (m, 8H aromatic), 6.78 (s, 2H, olefinic)	73.48	4.59	73.97	4.14
14.	Piperonal 7.5	4-Methoxy-benzoyl-propionic acid 10.4	(VII n) 12.1	76.1	115	—	—	—	71.65	4.54	70.80	4.38
15.	Piperonal 7.5	4-Methyl-benzoyl-propionic acid 9.6	(VII o) 12.0	82.1	190	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Contd. Table 1

AGNIHOTRI, PASARKAR & BAGAVANT : SYNTHESIS OF PERICARBONYL LIGNANS AND THEIR ANALOGUES

Sl. No.	Aldehyde g	β -Aroyl-propionic acid g	Lactone Yield		m.p. °C	UV E_{max}^{EtOH} nm (log ϵ)	IR cm ⁻¹	NMR δ	(Contd. Table I) Analysis %			
			g	%					Found		Calcd.	
16.	Piperonal 7.5	4-Ethyl-benzoyl-propionic acid 10.3	(VIIp) 10.0	65.4	137	-	-	-	C 74.59	H 4.75	C 74.99	H 5.04
17.	Piperonal 7.5	4-Isopropylbenzoyl-propionic acid 11.0	(VIIq) 14.3	85.1	114	-	-	-	C 75.25	H 5.67	C 75.44	H 5.43
18.	Piperonal 7.5	4-Chloro-benzoyl-propionic acid 10.6	(VIIr)	66.7	245	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

 TABLE 2— α -ARYLIDENE- β -BENZOYLPROPIONIC ACID (IX)

Sl. No.	R	Eq. wt. Found	Eq. wt. Calcd.	m.p. °C	UV λ_{max}^{EtOH} nm (log ϵ)	IR cm ⁻¹	NMR δ	Analysis %			
								Found		Calcd.	
1.	IXa : R ₁ = R ₂ = OCH ₃ , R' = H	323	326	169	233(4.17) 274(3.99) 398(3.85)	1681	-	C 70.41	H 5.12	C 69.93	H 5.56
2.	IXb : R ₁ = R ₂ = R' = OCH ₃	349	356	192	-	1681	-	C 67.82	H 5.56	C 67.40	H 5.66
3.	IXc : R ₁ = R ₂ = OCH ₃ , R' = CH ₃	338	340	196	-	1682	2.43 (s, 3H, -CH ₃) 3.63 and 3.80 (s, 6H, 2-OCH ₃) 4.23 (s, 2H, -CH ₂), 6.83-7.97 (m, 7H, aromatic and olefinic protons)	C 69.67	H 5.35	C 70.56	H 5.92
4.	IXd : R ₁ = OCH ₃ , R ₂ = OH, R' = H	317	312	207	233(4.39) 289(4.19)	-	-	C 69.63	H 4.92	C 69.23	H 5.16
5.	IXe : R ₁ = OCH ₃ , R ₂ = OH, R' = OCH ₃	339	342	211	-	1682	3.68 and 3.95 (s, 6H, 2-OCH ₃) 4.28 (s, 2H, -CH ₂) 7.14 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.90-8.10 (m, 8H, olefinic and aromatic protons)	C 66.90	H 5.06	C 66.66	H 5.30
6.	IXf : R ₁ = OCH ₃ , R ₂ = OH, R' = CH ₃	330	326	223	-	1681	-	C 70.41	H 5.25	C 69.93	H 5.56
7.	IXg : R ₁ = OCH ₃ , R ₂ = OH, R' =	348	354	163	-	1682	-	C 71.48	H 6.42	C 71.16	H 6.26
8.	IXh : R ₁ = OCH ₃ , R ₂ = OH, R' = Cl	341	346.5	213	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9.	IXi : R ₁ = OCH ₃	391.0	296	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	IXj : R ₁ = R' = H, R ₂ = OCH ₃	293	296	177	245(4.28) 275(4.30) 296(4.05)	-	-	C 73.24	H 6.03	C 72.98	H 5.44
11.	IXk : R ₁ = OCH ₃ , R ₂ = R' = H	291	296	145	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12.	IXl : R ₁ , R ₂ = -OCH ₂ O-, R' = H	307	310	203	237(4.42)	1682	4.30 (s, 2H, -CH ₂), 6.12 (s, 2H, -OCR ₂ O-), 6.98-8.2 (m, 9H, aromatic protons)	C 70.41	H 4.96	C 69.68	H 4.55
13.	IXm : R ₁ , R ₂ = -OCH ₂ O-, R' = OCH ₃	335	340	-	-	-	-	C 66.75	H 4.32	C 67.06	H 4.74
14.	IXn : R ₁ , R ₂ = -OCH ₂ O-, R' = CH ₃	320	324	196	-	-	-	C 69.92	H 4.78	C 70.37	H 4.97
15.	IXo : R ₁ , R ₂ = -OCH ₂ O-, R' = C ₂ H ₅	342	338	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.	IXp : R ₁ , R ₂ = -OCH ₂ O-, R' =	348	352	161	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
17.	IXq : R ₁ , R ₂ = -OCH ₂ O-, R' = Cl	337	344.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
18.	IXr : R ₁ = R' = OCH ₃ , R ₂ = H	326	326	142	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

TABLE 3— α -ARYLIDENE- β -METHYLENE- β -BENZOYLPROPIONIC ACIDS (XIV)

Sl. No.	R	Eq. wt. Found	Eq. wt. Calcd.	m. p. °C	UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} nm (log ϵ)	IR: cm^{-1}	NMR δ	Analysis %					
								Found		Calcd.			
		C	H	C	H								
1.	XIVa: $R_1 = R_2 = OCH_3$, $R' = H$	332	338	125	235 (4.21) 282 (4.08)	1660	3.82 and 3.90 (s, 6H, -2OCH ₃), 6.06 (s, 2H, -C=CH ₂), 6.8-8.0 (m, 9H, aromatic and olefinic protons)	70.65	5.02	71.00	5.36		
2.	XIVc: $R_1 = R' = OCH_3$, $R_2 = OH$	348	354	201	—	1660	—	67.41	5.34	67.80	5.12		
3.	XIVi: $R_1 = OCH_3$, $R_2 = R' = H$	302	308	170	—	—	—	73.68	5.31	74.02	5.23		
4.	XIVj: $R_1 = R' = H$, $R_2 = OCH_3$	304	308	144	—	—	—	—	—	—	—		
5.	XIVl: $R_1, R_2 = -OCH_2O-$, $R' = H$	317	322	—	—	1650	5.99-6.02 (d, 2H -C=CH ₂), 6.15 (s, 2H, -OCH ₂ O-), 6.93-8.0 (m, 9H, aromatic and olefinic protons)	71.24	4.09	70.80	4.38		

TABLE 4—1-PHENYL-2-CHLOROETHYL-NAPHTHALENE-3 CARBOXYLIC ACIDS

Sl. No.	R	Eq. wt. Found	Eq. wt. Calcd.	m. p. °C	UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} nm (log ϵ)	IR: cm^{-1}	NMR δ	Analysis %					
								Found		Calcd.			
		C	H	C	H								
1.	XVa: $R_1 = R_2 = OCH_3$, $R' = H$	351	356.8	217	235 (4.21) 282 (4.08)	1670	3.74 and 4.07 (s, 6H, 2-OCH ₃), 5.08 (s, 2H, -CH ₂ -Cl), 6.68 (s, 1H, C ₈ -H), 7.35 (s, 1H, C ₆ -H), 7.45-7.68 (m, 5H, phenyl) and 8.74 (s, 1H, C ₄ -H)	66.96	4.73	67.33	4.80		
2.	XVb: $R_1 = R_2 = R' = OCH_3$	380	386.8	179	—	1670	—	—	—	—	—		
3.	XVc: $R_1 = R_2 = OCH_3$, $R' = CH_3$	366	370.8	209	—	1671	—	67.79	5.01	68.02	5.16		
4.	XVd: $R_1 = OCH_3$, $R_2 = OH$, $R' = H$	335	342.8	179	—	1670	—	—	—	—	—		
5.	XVe: $R_1 = R' = OCH_3$, $R_2 = OH$	366	372.8	212	—	—	—	—	—	—	—		
6.	XVf: $R_1 = OCH_3$, $R_2 = OH$, $R' = CH_3$	352	356.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—		
7.	XVg: $R_1 = OCH_3$, $R_2 = OH$, $R' = \begin{matrix} H & & CH_3 \\ & \diagdown & / \\ & C & \\ & / & \diagdown \\ H & & CH_3 \end{matrix}$	380	384.8	196	—	1672	—	68.26	5.37	68.66	5.50		
8.	XVh: $R_1 = OCH_3$, $R_2 = R' = H$	321	326.8	201	—	—	—	—	—	—	—		
9.	XVI: $R_1 = R_2 = OCH_3$, $R_3 = H$	348	356.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—		
10.	XVIm: $R_1, R_2 = -OCH_2-$, $R' = H$	336	340.8	241	—	—	—	67.32	3.41	66.96	3.84		
11.	XVIn: $R_1, R_2 = OCH_2O-$, $R' = CH_3$	351	354.8	245	—	1671	—	67.47	4.56	67.70	4.26		
12.	XVl: $R_1, R_2 = -OCH_2O-$, $R' = \begin{matrix} CH_3 & & H \\ & \diagdown & / \\ & C & \\ & / & \diagdown \\ H & & CH_3 \end{matrix}$	376	382.8	229	—	—	—	68.77	4.69	69.01	5.00		

TABLE 5—1-ARYL-2-HYDROXYMETHYLNAPHTHALENE-3-CARBOXYLIC ACID LACTONES

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} nm (log ϵ)	IR cm^{-1}	NMR δ	Analysis %			
						Found C	H	Calcd. C	H
1. XVIa	$R_1 = R_2 = OCH_3, R' = H$	205	258 (4.69) 314 (4.02)	1760	3.85 and 4.06 (s, 6H, 2-OCH ₃), 5.22 (s, 2H, lactone CH ₂), 7.16 (s, 1H, C ₈ -H), 7.37 (s, 1H, C ₆ -H), 7.6 (br. s, 5H, phenyl) and 8.36 s, 1H, C ₄ -H)	75.04	5.39	74.99	5.04
2. XVIb	$R_1 = R_2 = R' = OCH_3$	230	—	1761	3.90, 4.01, 4.25 (s, 9H, 3-OCH ₃), 5.30 (s, 2H, lactone CH ₂), 7.1-7.7 (m, 6H, aromatic), 8.4 (s, 1H, C ₄ -H)	72.37	4.86	72.00	5.18
3. XVIc	$R_1 = R_2 = OCH_3, R' = CH_3$	214	—	1762	2.50 (s, 3H, -CH ₃), 3.86 and 4.08 (s, 6H, 2-OCH ₃), 5.23 (s, 1H, lactone CH ₂), 7.16-7.40 (m, 6H, aromatic), 8.33 (s, 1H, C ₄ -H)	75.39	5.24	75.44	5.43
4. XVI d	$R_1 = OCH_3, R_2 = OH, R' = OCH_3$	220	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
5. XVIe	$R_1 = OCH_3, R_2 = OH, R' = CH_3$	241	—	1760	2.47 (s, 3H, -CH ₃), 3.83 (s, 3H, -1 OCH ₃), 5.20 (s, 2H, lactone CH ₂), 7.04-7.30 (m, 7H and 1H, -OH aromatic) 8.25 (s, 1H, C ₄ -H)	74.68	4.73	74.99	5.04
6. XVI f	$R_1 = OCH_3, R_2 = OH, R' = \begin{matrix} H \\ \\ C \\ / \backslash \\ CH_3 \end{matrix}$	244	—	1762	—	76.06	5.45	75.83	5.79
7. XVI g	$R_1 = OCH_3, R_2 = H', R' = H$	172	—	—	3.97 (s, 3H, -OCH ₃), 5.21 (s, 2H, lactone CH ₂), 7.17-7.83 (m, 8H, aromatic), 8.33 (s, 1H, C ₄ -H)	78.25	4.34	78.60	4.86
8. XVI h	$R_1, R_2 = OCH_2O-, R' = H$	211	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
9. XVI i	$R_1, R_2 = OCH_2O-, R' = CH_3$	171	—	1672	2.50 (s, 3H, -CH ₃), 5.23 (s, 2H, lactone CH ₂), 6.10 (s, 2H, -OCH ₂ O-), 7.13 - 7.4 (d, 6H aromatic), 2.28 (s, 1H, C ₄ -H)	75.19	4.23	75.46	4.43
10. XVI j	$R_1, R_2 = -OCH_2O-, R' = \begin{matrix} H \\ \\ C \\ / \backslash \\ CH_3 \end{matrix}$	241	—	—	—	76.73	4.87	76.29	5.24

red with HCl (3N). It gave a solid which was crystallized and identified as α -(3,4-dimethoxybenzylidene)- β -benzoylpropionic acid (4.6 g). Recrystallized from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 169°. Eq. wt. Found 324; Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈O₅; 326. IR: ν_{CO} (nujol) 1650 cm⁻¹ (α, β -unsaturated ketone and carboxylic acid). (Found: C, 70.41; H, 5.12. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈O₅; C, 69.92 H, 5.56%). Table 2 presents data for other acids (IXa-IXr).

3. α -(3,4-Dimethoxybenzylidene)- β -methylene- β -benzoylpropionic acid (XIVa, R₁=R₂=OCH₃, R'=H):

To a solution of α -(3,4-dimethoxybenzylidene)- β -benzoylpropionic acid (IXa) in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide (9 ml) was added 40% formalin solution (6 ml) and the reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. It was then cooled, acidified and extracted with benzene (3 × 50 ml) and dried (MgSO₄). Evaporation of the solvent led to an orange gum (2.3 g) crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60) to give a solid, m.p. 125-126°, which was identified as α -(3,4-dimethoxybenzylidene)- β -methylene- β -benzoylpropionic acid. UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 235 nm (log ϵ 4.21) and 282 nm (log ϵ 4.08). IR: ν_{CO} (nujol) 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=O and CO₂H merged). NMR: (CDCl₃) δ 3.82 and 3.90 (s, 6H, 2-OCH₃), 6.06 (s, 2H, C=CH₂), 6.8-8.0 (m, 9H,

aromatic and olefinic protons). Table 3 presents data for other methylenic compounds (XIVa-XIVl).

4. 1-Phenyl-2-chloromethyl-6,7-dimethoxynaphthalene-3-carboxylic acid (XVa, R₁=R₂=OCH₃, R'=H):

Conc. hydrochloric acid (50 ml) was gradually added to a cold solution of α -(3,4-dimethoxybenzylidene)- β -methylene- β -benzoylpropionic acid (XIVa) (2.6 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and the mixture left overnight at room temperature. The yellow precipitate (2.2 g) formed was collected and crystallized from methanol to give a pale yellow solid, m.p. 217°, Eq. wt. Found 355; Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₇O₄Cl; 356.5. UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 252 (log ϵ 4.79) and 287 (log ϵ 3.93). IR: ν_{CO} (KBr) 1670 cm⁻¹ (COOH gr). NMR: (CDCl₃) δ 3.74 and 4.07 (s, 6H, 2-OCH₃), 5.08 (s, 2H, -CH₂Cl), 6.68 (s, 1H, C₈-H), 7.35 (s, 1H, C₂-H), 7.45-7.68 (m, 5H, phenyl) and 8.74 (s, 1H, C₄-H). (Found: C, 66.96; H, 4.73. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₇O₄Cl; C, 67.33; H, 4.80%). Table 4 presents data for other chloromethyl derivatives (XVa-XV o).

5. 1-Phenyl-2-hydroxymethyl-6,7-dimethoxynaphthalene-3-carboxylic acid lactone (XVIa, R₁=R₂=OCH₃, R'=H):

The chloromethylnaphthoic acid (XVa) (2.0 g) was dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide (15 ml) and

Scheme 3

heated at 100° for 1 hr. The mixture was cooled and washed with water to give a yellow solid (1.7 g). Crystallization from chloroform-methanol gave light yellow prisms, m.p. 205°, of 1-phenyl-2-hydroxymethyl-6,7-dimethoxynaphthalene-3-carboxylic acid lactone (XVIa). UV: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 258 (log ϵ 4.69) and 314 nm (log ϵ 4.02). IR: ν_{CO} (KBr) 1670 cm^{-1} (lactone). NMR: CDCl_3 δ 3.85 and 4.06 (s, 6H, 2-OCH₃), 5.22 (s, 2H, lactone CH₂), 7.16 (s, 1H, C₈-H), 7.37 (s, 1H, C₂-H), 7.16 (br, s, 5H phenyl) and 8.36 (s, 1H, C₄-H). Table 5 presents data for other pericarboxyl lactones (XVIa-XVIj).

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References

- 1a. H. KOFOD and J. JORGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, 8, 941, 1296; 1955, 9, 346.
- 1b. T. MURAKAMI and A. MATSUSHIMA, *Yakagaku Zaashi*, 1961, 81, 1596.
- 1c. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, S. S. SATHE, N. VISHWANATHAN, B. R. PAI and M. SHRINIVASAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1967, 3517.
- 1d. Z. HORII, K. OHKAWA, S. KIM and T. MOMOSE, *Chem. Comm.*, 1968, 653.
- 1e. K. MUNAKATA, S. MARUMO, K. OHTA and Y-L CHEN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1967, 4167.
- 1f. K. OHTA and K. MUNAKATA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1970, 923.
- 1g. M. OKIGAWA, T. MAEDA and N. KAWANO, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1970, 18, 862.
- 1h. K. WADA and K. MUNAKATA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1970, 2017.
- 1i. R. D. HAWORTH and W. KELLY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 745.
- 1j. Y-T LIN, T-B LO, K-T HANG and B. WEINSTEIN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1967, 849.
- 1k. Z. HORII, M. TSUJUCHI and T. MOMOSE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1969, 1079.
- 1l. H. MACLEAN and B. L. MACDONALD, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1969, 47, 457.
- 1m. H. MACLEAN and B. F. MACDONALD, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1969, 47, 4495.
- 1n. R. S. BURDEN, L. CROMBIE and D. WHITING, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1968, 1035; *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1969, 693.
2. T. MURAKAMI and A. MATSUSHIMA, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1961, 81, 1596.
3. K. MUNAKATA, S. MARUMO, K. OHTA and Y-L CHEN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1965, 4167.
4. A. G. GONZALEZ and V. DARIUM, *Planta Med.*, 1979, 36, 200; *Chem. Abs.*, 1979, 91, 186441.
5. P. A. GANESHPURE, Ph.D. Thesis, Nagpur University, 1977.
6. A. I. SCOTT, "Interpretation of the UV Spectra of Natural Products", Pergamon Press, London, 1969, p. 79.
7. C. N. R. RAO, "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, London, 1963, p. 193.
8. V. R. PASARKAR, Ph.D. Thesis, Nagpur University, 1977.
9. W. BORSCHKE, *Ber.*, 1904, 47, 1108.
10. N. H. CROMWELL and R. A. SETTERQUIST, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 22, 116.
11. E. L. ELIEL, "Stereochemistry of Carbon Compounds", McGraw Hill Book Company, Inc., New York, 1962, p. 92.
12. H. E. ZIMMERMAN and ABRAMJIAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 2086.
13. V. P. BARVE, A. B. KULKARNI and A. P. WAGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 84.
14. A. P. WAGH and A. B. KULKARNI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13B, 882.
15. R. D. HAWORTH and G. SHELDRIK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 636.
16. A. S. R. ANJANEU, V. R. RAO, P. SATYANARAYANA and L. R. ROW, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 203.
17. S. GHOSAL, R. P. S. CHAUHAN and R. S. SHRIVASTAVA, *Phytochemistry*, 1974, 13, 1933.